

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 5-11 October 2024
Report published: September 2025

Little and large: surveying and
safeguarding coral reefs & whale
sharks in the Maldives

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Abstract

In October 2024, Biosphere Expeditions ran its 12th annual Reef Check survey expedition to the Maldives. International citizen scientists, supervised by a professional coral reef biologist, performed Reef Check surveys for one week at South Male' atoll at semi-exposed and sheltered sites. We repeated visits to three sites last surveyed in 2022 in this atoll.

The expedition was hampered by very strong winds, which scuppered plans to survey three long-term monitoring locations in the southern part of the atoll, as well as Vaavu atoll to the south. A mass coral bleaching event occurred in April and May 2024, following on from the last significant bleaching event in 2022. The Maldives faced eight degree heating weeks (above the long-term average and bleaching threshold temperature of 30 degrees Celsius) in May & June, but it appears from local reports that the 2024 event has had less impact than the 2016 event.

Hard corals were affected at the Guraidhoo backreef site by disease in the deeper transect, probably due to increased sedimentation from land reclamation less than 1000 m away, which took place in 2020. The literature has linked increased sedimentation to increased occurrence of white-band disease in *Acropora*. A similar increase in occurrence of that disease was reported from the Guraidhoo backreef site. Surveys found only one colony affected by brown disease at Guraidhoo banana reef, which is a more exposed site.

Predation by *Drupella* snails was patchy in intensity, but occurred consistently at all sites. At Guraidhoo forereef and Beybe's sheltered shallow transect, sites with very different exposures and hard coral species, there was considerable *Drupella* predation, with 14 colonies affected at Guraidhoo and five at Beybe's.

Despite the threats from bleaching and sedimentation from land reclamation (at Guraidhoo sites), coral cover has not changed dramatically since the 2019 surveys (monitored before earthworks commenced). Guraidhoo backreef presented an overall increase in hard coral cover of 3% (28 to 31%). Guraidhoo forereef increased by 5% (20 to 25%), as did Beybe's (31 to 36%). It is noteworthy that most of the hard corals at Guraidhoo backreef and Beybe's were reasonably bleaching-tolerant forms (compared to forereefs that are more dominated by branching and digitate *Acropora* and *Pocillopora*).

Fish populations of the snapper family (particularly humpback snapper *Lutjanus gibbus*) were recorded at moderate levels, particularly at Bandos house reef in North Male' atoll. This site (a protected site by virtue of being next to a resort) also had sweetlips at densities higher than at other sites. Other commercially important species were rarely recorded or small in size at all sites, including trevally (almost entirely absent), large emperors and large groupers (none over 50 cm). Other species of snapper that should occur on forereefs were absent from all survey sites (such as the black and white snapper *Macolor niger* and red snapper *Lutjanus bohar*).

One triton trumpet shell was recorded – only the second reported from our 15 years of Reef Check expeditions. Two lobsters were recorded, one at Bandos house reef and one at shallow Guraidhoo.

'Rare' / charismatic animals encountered were black and white tip reef sharks and nurse sharks. A reef manta, six mobular and two eagle rays were recorded at Guradhoor forereef site, which is located just to the south of a reef channel.

Overall, key threats to coral reefs (climate breakdown with increased sea surface temperature, seawater acidification, overfishing, sedimentation and inappropriate/unsustainable atoll development, poor water treatment and solid waste accumulation) have remained in place since expeditions began with little sign of national or local (or indeed global) authorities and corporations willing to tackle these. In fact, trajectories are not encouraging and we may be recording the slow decline of coral reefs in the Maldives, as elsewhere in the tropics, where (on only a 1.5 degrees trajectory) 70-90% of all tropical coral reefs worldwide are likely to succumb to climate breakdown by 2050, along according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). In the Maldives, inner backreefs in particular seem doomed to disappear within our lifetimes unless drastic action, which is nowhere to be seen, is taken. Outer forereefs, exposed to colder oceanic waters and upwellings, may fare better in the short and medium-term. The authors were the first to notice this pattern and call it the 'inner/outer reef dichotomy'.

A new paper (Pancrazi et al. 2025), co-authored by the report authors, and heavily relying on Reef Check data collected by the expeditions, has corroborated this dichotomy pattern pre- and post the 2016 bleaching event. The paper illustrates typical trajectories of 'recovery' of coral reefs, first recorded in Biosphere Expedition reports: There is poor recovery of diversity of lifeforms and species from most inner (lagoonal) reefs, with only smaller and slow-growing bleaching-tolerant lifeforms persisting in most of the dive locations. This is alarming, because - whilst our observations are from a few (10's) of sites visited every other year - incidental reports and spot-dives from other locations show similar trends of decline in the diversity of species, lifeforms and the very seascape on which the islands are built.

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1. Expedition review

1.1. Background

Background information, location, conditions and the general research area are as described in [Solandt & Hammer \(2019\)](#).

1.2. Dates & team

The 2024 annual Reef Check survey ran over one week from 5 to 11 October 2024 with a team of international citizen scientists, a professional scientist, and an expedition leader.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities, and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence): Jenan Al Asfoor (Oman), Rayman Aryani (USA), Sarah Coad (Canada), Tim de Gier (Netherlands), Hooi Ling Eng (UK), Lukas Hammer (Germany), Karina Kempers (Switzerland), Alison Lee (USA), Chai Hong Lim (UK), Arnav Mathur* (India), Carsten Riedl** (Germany), Paula Thomsen (UK).

*blogger, see [blog](#), [LinkedIn post](#), [picture & video archive](#)

**blogger, see [newspaper article](#) (in German)

Figure 1.2a. Expedition team 2024.

The expedition scientist was Dr. Jean-Luc Solandt, a Londoner with a degree in Marine Biology from the University of Liverpool. After graduating, he spent a year working on the Great Barrier Reef assisting field scientists in studies on fisheries, and the ecology of soft corals and damselfish. He returned to the UK and enrolled in a Ph.D. in sea urchin ecology in Jamaica, based both in London and Jamaica. He went on to be an expedition science co-ordinator for projects in Tanzania, the Philippines and Fiji, and has successfully undertaken campaign, science and policy work in planning and managing Marine Protected Areas in the UK and western Europe since 2008. He has been the Reef Check co-ordinator for the Maldives since 2005, and has thus far led 11 expeditions to the islands. Jean-Luc has over 1100 dives clocked up since he first trained to be a marine biologist 32 years ago.

The expedition was led by Dr. Matthias Hammer, who founded Biosphere Expeditions in 1999. Born in Germany, he went to school there, before joining the Army, and serving for several years amongst other units with the German Parachute Regiment. After active service he came to the UK and was educated at St Andrews, Oxford and Cambridge. During his time at university he either organised or was involved in the running of several expeditions, some of which were conservation expeditions (for example to the Brazilian Amazon and Madagascar), whilst others were mountaineering/climbing expeditions (for example to the Russian Caucasus, the Alps or the Rocky Mountains). With Biosphere Expeditions he has led teams all over the globe. He is a qualified wilderness medical officer, ski instructor, mountain leader, divemaster and survival skills instructor. Once a rower on the international circuit, he is now an amateur marathon runner and Ironman triathlete.

Jenan Alasfoor supported the teaching and training effort in her role as Reef Check trainer.

1.3. Partners

On this project Biosphere Expeditions worked with Reef Check, 'Save the Beach' Maldives, the Marine Conservation Society, the Maldives Marine Research Centre (MRC) of the Ministry of Fisheries and Agriculture, Maldives Whale Shark Research Programme (MWSRP), Land and Marine Environmental Resource (LaMer) Group and the MV Theia liveboard.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions, which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as citizen scientists, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Thank you to all of you and the ones we have not managed to mention by name (you know who you are) for making it all happen. Thank you to the crew of [MV Theia](#), our liveboard expedition base, for being such excellent and capable hosts. Thank you also to Hussein Zahir of LaMer for guidance and advice. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support. We also thank Irene Pancrazi, Irene Sibille, Arianna Verardo, Hassan Ahmed, Valentina Asnaghi and Monica Montefalcone for publishing a paper (Pancrazi et al. 2025) on Maldives Reef Check data with us, and the anonymous reviewers of this report. Finally, thank you to Carsten Riedl for supplying most of the photos in this report.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

Additional background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

A multimedia expedition diary is available on <https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/maldives-2024/>.

This report and all other expedition reports for the Maldives and other expeditions are available on <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each participating citizen scientist paid towards expedition costs a contribution of €2,880 per seven-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, all maps and special non-personal equipment, all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs, etc., as well as visas and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how these contributions were spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	34,324
Expenditure	
Staff includes local & international salaries, travel, and expenses	5,169
Research includes equipment and other research expenses	321
Transport includes taxis and other local transport	0
Base includes board, lodging and other live-aboard services	24,598
Administration includes some admin and miscellaneous costs	97
Team recruitment Maldives as estimated % of PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	9,768
Income – Expenditure	-5,629
Total percentage spent directly on project	116%*

*This means that in 2024, the expedition ran at a loss and was supported over and above the income from the expedition contributions and grants by Biosphere Expeditions.

2. Reef Check survey

2.1. Introduction and background

Review up to 2024

A review of the rationale for the expedition and the situation of the Maldives up to 2019 is described in Solandt & Hammer (2020). This includes sub-chapters on Maldivian coral reefs, fisheries, coral bleaching, previous Reef Check surveys, descriptions of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), governance and management, as well as the 1998 and 2015/2016 bleaching events.

This is the twelfth annual expedition since 2011 (all expedition reports [here](#), no expeditions due to COVID-19 in 2020/21). There was a minor bleaching event in June 2020, but online forums suggest that this did not affect populations of hard corals in the Maldives significantly. Expeditions in 2019 and 2022 were in South Male' and Vaavu atolls, partly to monitor new reef locations, and partly due to a lack of recovery of the North and South Ari atoll reefs in 2018. In 2023, we changed our expedition location to the original survey sites from North Ari, to see if there had been significant changes in hard coral cover, lifeforms, and patterns seven years after the 2016 bleaching event (Solandt and Hammer 2019). At the last time of visiting these sites, the inner reefs (Dega Thilla and Kudafalhu) were particularly badly affected by coral bleaching from the 2016 event. The 2023 expedition showed a mixed recovery from bleaching with some reefs (e.g. Kudafalhu) showing considerable recovery from 1 - 4% hard coral cover to over 40% for *Acropora* corals. Another inner reef (Dega Thilla) that had a *Discosoma*¹ infestation on the deeper (7 m) transect now also has these coral-smothering animals on the shallow transect (1 – 3 m). This is an expansion in coverage since the previous surveys of the site (Solandt and Hammer 2024), with an irreversible phase shift to a *Discosoma* “reef” likely to occur.

There is no change to the summary of threats to Maldives coral reefs, both on the local anthropogenic and global climate-induced level. As bleaching events increase in frequency and intensity, the recovery period between events is shortening, reducing hard coral complexity, diversity and cover as well as overall reef rugosity. Pisapia et al. (2016) postulated that after the 1998 (initial global) bleaching event, coral reefs of the Maldives took at least a decade to recover.

Key threats are:

- Climate breakdown and associated sea surface temperature increases leading to coral bleaching (from human-caused increases in atmospheric CO₂ concentration)
- Increased levels of ocean acidification (atmospheric CO₂ dissolving in seawater); which leads to decreased skeletal strength of calcium carbonate-dependent corals, decreased growth rates and lower reproductive output for reef-building corals
- Overfishing of keystone reef fish and invertebrate species (e.g. predators of Crown-of-Thorns and herbivorous fish)
- Sedimentation and inappropriate/unsustainable atoll development

¹ *Discosoma* spp. is a genus of Corallimorph, a soft-bodied relative of hard corals

- Poor wastewater treatment leading to coastal pollution and eutrophication
- Solid waste pollution with direct and indirect negative effects on marine species

The Maldives have semi-autonomous atoll councils that have some powers of local decision-making, particularly with regard to reef fishing. As a result, some of the recommendations from past reports have been met with resistance. The provision to increase the minimum landing sizes for some species targeted by grouper trade is one example. Given the small sizes of many species seen in the wild, as outlined in previous reports (Solandt and Hammer 2015, 2017a, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2023, 2024, Solandt et al. 2016), it is regrettable that the trajectory for the Maldives overfishing of reef fish species affects local and national fishery revenues and the reef fish populations of harvested species.

A [Blue Marine Foundation](#) project works in the southern Maldives, with resort partners and the government, to reform fisheries management at Laamu atoll². This work has since created a new NGO called [Maldives Resilient Reefs](#) (MRR). MRR research from Laamu has shown that reef fish resources are now being exploited by heavier lined ‘jig’ fishing on the outer reef slope. This is leading to a greater exploitation of new stocks at, or around, 100 m depth, as much of the shallow reef fish populations are now denuded. Further survey work at Laamu has involved social science and resource use discussions with resort and local islands. There is an attempt in Laamu to get local atoll councils involved in delivering fisheries management measures, particularly with resorts. Some fishers have signed up to monitoring of their positions for potential future management with digital satellite tracking technology, whilst there are engagement and education programmes to promote environmental stewardship amongst the atoll community. Such transparency of fishing activity using digital tracking hardware and software has been supported by Minister Shiyam at the recent UN Oceans Conference in Nice (June 2025)³. MRR have also been successful at campaigning to stop a call for long-lining (August 2024). This excellent campaign has protected the pole and line fishery from overfishing⁴ and our hope is that the resorts within the atoll sign up to sustainable fisheries management so that local fishers and resorts can act together to develop a long-term reduction in fishing pressure.

Due to past political interference in the rule of law and due process, there were several developments that were patently counterproductive to the Maldives environment under previous governments. Profit-driven resort development, and other major capital infrastructure project investments from overseas, were permitted despite environmental concerns raised by The Environment Protection Agency (EPA) and MRC. Decisions by the EPA were effectively rejected by the tourism ministry⁵. In 2024 there was a cessation of resort building during the April-June bleaching period ‘to reduce the stress on corals’ that was supported by coral experts⁶. However, there are reports of some developments not being prosecuted for breaches to dredging license conditions⁷. Inappropriate development is not necessarily that different in western democracies, where there is an inability of citizens to challenge decisions in court due to prohibitive expense.

² <http://www.bluemarinefoundation.com/project/maldives/>

³ [Maldives Commits to Data-Driven Fisheries Reform and Marine Protection at UNOC3](#)

⁴ <https://www.bluemarinefoundation.com/2025/02/17/against-longlining/>

⁵ <http://www.climatechangenews.com/2017/03/20/maldives-regime-imperils-coral-reefs-dash-cash/>

⁶ [Maldives Halts Coastal Development Projects – The Diplomat](#)

⁷ [Adhadhu - Concern as reclamation work continues despite EPA order](#)

2024 was another year of mass coral bleaching in the Maldives as part of the Fourth Global Bleaching Event, although the impacts appear to have been smaller compared to those of the 2016 global bleaching event. Figure 2.1. shows the extended eight-week period when sea surface temperature (SST) was above the 30-degree threshold for a bleaching event.

Figure 2.1a. SSTs for 2024 including the bleaching period (April – June)

2.2. Methods and planning

Biosphere Expeditions uses the [Reef Check methodology](#) for its coral reef surveys (see Solandt and Hammer 2015, 2017a, 2018, 2019, Solandt et al. 2016 and earlier reports on www.biosphere-expeditions.org/reports for details). The 2024 surveys were a repeat of the 2019 and 2022 survey locations in the east of the archipelago.

It is worth noting that Reef Check is particularly effective at accurately recording benthic lifeforms (substrate), invertebrates and charismatic species. However, Done et al. (2017) noted that it appears less effective at recording accurate reef fish population data, as volunteers, although passing tests in the classroom and field, can regularly confuse families (e.g. emperors Lethrinids with snappers Lutjanids), and indeed mis-identify some charismatic species on the fish list (e.g. bumphead parrotfish).

We surveyed five reef sites (see Table 2.3a), attempting to repeat surveys carried out in 2022 (Solandt and Hammer 2023) and going back to 2019 when we first surveyed these sites (Solandt and Hammer, 2020). Training was conducted at Guraidhoo in South Male' atoll. All reef sites were within North Male' atoll as inclement weather (see Fig. 2.2a) prevented us from leaving the atoll. The sites were: Guraidhoo backreef and forereef, Beybe's bellybutton, Guraidhoo banana (new site) and Bandos Island house reef (new site). Shallow dives using SCUBA were between 3 and 6 m, with deeper dives from 7 to 10 m.

All training was completed on board the MV Theia during the first three days of the expedition. Biosphere Expeditions recruited citizen scientists, carried out logistics, and provided health and safety on board the research vessel. The scientific programme, training, data collection, and analysis was led by Dr Jean-Luc Solandt (Reef Check Course Director) and supported by Dr Matthias Hammer (Reef Check Course Director) as well as Reef Check Trainer Jenan Alasfoor.

Figure 2.2a. The expedition was badly affected by high winds and heavy rains, including days when the government announced a ban on all in- and on-water activities; a situation unprecedented from all preceding years (since 2011).

Figure 2.2b. MV Theia (liveaboard vessel, right) and dhoni (left).
Diving took place from the dhoni that deployed and collected all divers from the main vessel.

Figure 2.2c. 100 m transect tapes were laid at two depths: 3 – 6 m (shallow) and 7 – 10 m (deep).

Figure 2.2d. Training took place aboard the MV Theia, using Powerpoint presentations, in-water ID, background lectures & tests.

Figure 2.2e. Data entry and quality assessment happened on board the main vessel straight after survey dives. Divers used pre-printed slates to record data that was checked by experienced Reef Check instructors during data entry.

2.3. Results

Sites surveyed

[Sites surveyed during the 2024 expedition](#) were a mixture of inner atoll sites (thilas and giris) and an outer reef slope south of Guraidhoo. Sites (Table 2.3a and Figure 2.3a) were surveyed based on accessibility to Male' during week-long live-aboard expeditions, exposure, a mix of inner and outer reefs, and because they demonstrated a typical range of Maldivian reefs. Inclement weather prevented us from visiting sites in Vaavu atoll.

Table 2.3a. Site names and locations. See also [online map](#) and Figure 2.3a below.

Site name	Date	Latitude	Longitude	Inner / outer reef	Atoll
Guraidhoo backreef	8.10.24	3.905082 N	73.457402 E	Inner	South Male'
Guraidhoo forereef	9.10.24	3.884616 N	73.0016 E	Outer	South Male'
Beybe's bellybutton	8.10.24	3 53.583 N	73 24.2 E	Inner	South Male'
Guraidhoo banana	7.10.24	3.894489 N	73.459495 E	Inner	South Male'
Bandos House Reef	10.10.24	4 16.135 N	73 29.7 E	Inner	North Male'
Ranikan Outer	N/A	Not visited			
Farish Faru	N/A	Not visited			
Kuda fushi	N/A	Not visited			

Figure 2.3a. Central Maldives atolls with survey locations (see also [online map](#)).

Coral cover

Hard coral cover (HC) ranged from 20% at deep Guraidhoo banana reef up to 44.4% at deep Bandos House reef (9 m). The amount of bare rock (RC) had the highest combined value at Baros house reef (48% shallow; 31% deep) and at Guraidhoo forereef (49% shallow; 44% deep). The most rubble (RB) was recorded from shallow Guraidhoo banana reef (46%).

Figure 2.3b. Mean benthic cover at 3-4 m (shallow – upper chart) and 7-10 m (deep – lower chart) at five sites surveyed in October 2024. Benthic categories are: HC – Hard Coral; RKC – Recently Killed Coral; NIA – Nutrient Indicator Algae; SP – Sponge; RC – Rock; RB – Rubble; SD – Sand; OT – Other.

Figure 2.3c. Benthic cover at Bandos House reef illustrating a grazed substrate suitable for coral recruitment. Note the relatively small size of existing living corals.

Changes in hard coral cover (comparing 2024 surveys to 2019 for three sites)

Hard coral (HC) cover ranged from 21% at Guraidhoo forereef shallow, up to Beybe’s shallow (3 m) at 43% in 2024. An increase in hard coral cover was observed at the two Guraidhoo sites (backreef and forereef) and at Beybe’s between 2019 and 2024 (Fig 2.3d).

Figure 2.3d. Mean benthic cover at 3-4 m (shallow – upper chart) and 7-10 m (deep – lower chart) at three sites surveyed in 2019 and 2024 from three permanent monitoring sites, Guraidhoo backreef, Guraidhoo forereef and Beybe’s bellybutton. Categories recorded are: HC – Hard Coral; NIA – Nutrient Indicator Algae; SP – Sponge; RC – Rock; RB – Rubble; SD – Sand; OT – Other. Sites are Guraidhoo backreef, forereef and Beybe’s.

The sites with the greatest change in hard coral cover since 2019 was at Guraidhoo forereef deep (9 m) where the coral cover increased from 18% to 29%. The second highest increase in hard coral cover was at Beybe’s forereef shallow, which increased from 36% to 43%. In 2019 there was a relatively high number of Crown of Thorns starfish recorded on the survey (two individuals), and a further four individuals observed off transect.

Reef Fish populations

There was little difference between sites for most reef fish groups. However, the numbers of planktonic butterflyfish *Heniochus* spp – a school of about 150 animals – and humpback snapper *Lutjanus gibbus* at Bandos House Reef were considerably high. At Guraidhoo backreef, humpback snapper were the dominant snapper species. Although the humpback snapper can attain a size of 50 cm in length, no individuals were recorded above 25 cm. This snapper species is not usually seen in shallow exposed reefs, and was reported at higher densities at Beybe’s and Guraidhoo backreef at highly sheltered sites.

Figure 2.3e. Fish populations (per 500m³ replicate) from all sites surveyed in 2024 at a shallow (top) and deep (bottom) transect. Parrotfish are only recorded over 20 cm. *Grouper data are from animals over 30 cm, and aggregated from all size categories. No grouper over 50 cm were recorded on any survey.

Figure 2.3f. Grouper – the most popular food fish on the reef is now rare (at large size) on the reef. The epinephelid grouper family *Epinephelus coeruleopunctatus* used to be reasonably common in the Maldives before 2000 (Maldives Fisheries Ministry 2020). This small epinephelid specimen (<50 cm) was recorded off transect.

Unusual sightings

Reef Check surveys also record marine megafauna off-transect (e.g. sharks, turtles, rays, cetaceans, bumphead parrotfish and napoleon wrasse). Unusual and notable observations of high numbers of species were also recorded such as giant clams and triton's trumpet shell – a very rare occurrence for Reef Check surveys, with only one other such shell recorded on a leisure dive, during a snorkel on a resort house reef in 2012.

Table 2.3b Unusual sightings at the five reef check sites. Note the greater numbers of large fish sightings at offshore and more exposed sites (Guraidhoo forereef, Guraidhoo Banana and Bandos House reef).

	Guraidhoo backreef	Guraidhoo forereef	Beybe's Bellybutton	Guraidhoo Banana reef	Bandos rouse reef
Sharks		1 whitetip 1 blacktip		2 blacktip 1 nurse shark	3 blacktip
Turtles		2 hawksbill		2 hawksbill	2 hawksbill
Rays		Manta 2 eagle rays 6 mobular rays			
Fish		Moray eel (off transect)		Small tooth jobfish 2 dogtooth tuna	
Other		1 lobster off transect			1 lobster

Figure 2.3g. Lobster at Bandos house reef.

Figure 2.3h. Humpback snapper *L. gibbus* at Bandos house reef.

Figure 2.3i. A blacktip reef shark at Bandos house reef.

Figure 2.3j. A hawksbill at Bandos house reef.

Figure 2.3k. Pilot whales were observed on our journey from the airport to the Guraidhoo area in South Male' along the outer reef to the northeast (outer) part of South Male' atoll.

Figure 2.3i. A nurse shark observed at Bandos house reef.

Invertebrate populations

Invertebrate populations for keystone species such as *Diadema* urchins (important grazer), collector urchins (food species), tritons trumpet shell (valuable as a curio) and lobster (food) were scarce or absent at the sites surveyed. There were one single banded shrimp and two lobsters at Bandos house reef (where fishing is restricted) (Fig. 2.3b). Species of commercially collectable sea cucumber (both ‘pinkfish’ *Holothuria edulis*) were also recorded from Bandos house reef. A single triton shell was recorded at Guraidhoo forereef.

Impacts

Drupella corallivorous snails were recorded (as coral damage) at all sites apart from Guraidhoo Banana (Fig. 2.3m). At Guraidhoo (deep) forereef, one replicate 20 m section of the survey had 14 colonies affected by these animals (Fig. 2.3n). *Drupella* were also recorded on five colonies at Beybe’s shallow transect with associated coral mortality. White-band disease was recorded on six *Acropora* colonies at Guraidhoo backreef at the deep transect, in a location close to the reclaimed island area (within 1000 m) to the east (see Fig. 2.3o). There were considerable coral feeding scars from parrotfish at Guraidhoo forereef on the shallow transect on living *Porites* coral blocks (Fig. 2.3p).

Five relatively small hard coral colonies were almost completely bleached in the shallow reef at Beybe’s. A coral colony at the deep Guraidhoo banana reef had brown band disease. Bleaching occurred on every replicate transect of the deeper Bandos house reef site, but with only a small proportion of the overall live coral population along the transect affected. Where colonies did show bleaching stress, the majority of the colony’s living tissue was affected.

None of the reefs surveyed were damaged by *Discosoma* corallimorphs that have colonised some vulnerable post-bleached coral reefs of the Maldives (Solandt and Hammer 2024). This invasive species was previously found at some sites and is thought to be related to nutrient enrichment from land-based pollution. *Discosoma* can smother the dead coral reef framework, causing a phase shift that precludes coral recovery (Norstrom et al. 2009).

Figure 2.3m. Impacts (shallow 3 – 6 m above) and deep (6 – 10 m below) recorded using a semi-quantitative scale. 1:1-3; 2:4-5; 3:>5 occurrences of that particular impact per 100 sqm replicate area. Coral damage 'other' is usually *Drupella* predation (particularly at deep Guraidhoo forereef on 14 colonies, shallow Beybe's with five colonies affected).

Figure 2.3n. *Drupella* predation on *Acropora* colony.

Figure 2.3o. White-band disease on *Acropora* sp..

Figure 2.3p. Parrotfish predation and grazing scars are seen on exposed outer reefs, particularly on these lobed *Porites* corals.

2.4. Discussion and conclusions

The inner/outer reef dichotomy

We saw limited evidence of mass coral bleaching during our expedition. There was evidence of bleaching to some young colonies of *Acropora* and *Pocillopora*. More resilient lifeforms such as *Porites rus* appeared to show paling, a sign of imminent or past bleaching (Fig. 2.4a)

Overall, surveyed hard corals did not show significant bleaching, but coral disease was evident, particularly at Guraidhoo backreef, which has been subjected to increased sediment loading from land reclamation works since 2020 (Solandt and Hammer 2020, Solandt and Hammer 2023). This has had clear negative impacts on hard coral cover: At shallow backreef Guraidhoo, the hard coral cover was at 30% in 2019 (pre-land reclamation) and decreased to 14% (2022 surveys), but then increased to 34% (2024 surveys). Guraidhoo forereef shows a similar transition from 21% (2019) to 15% (2022) to 21% (2025). This indicates resilience in the face of both sedimentation and potential pollutants being released into the lagoonal waters in the shallow reef areas (from the reclamation works). Also, as there was a major coral bleaching event in April-June 2024, there appears to have been a resistance to that affect given the recorded hard coral cover at these two sites.

Figure 2.4a. *Porites rus* at Bandos House reef showing signs of stress (paling) that may be as a result of increased SST during the previous April-June period. This is one of the most bleaching resistant coral lifeforms that has been very successful at colonising post-bleaching Maldives reefs.

Deeper Guraidhoo backreef sites showed more diseased colonies (table *Acropora* colonies) compared to other sites (Fig. 3.2n). The site had six colonies exhibiting this impact in the deeper transect where wave action is weaker and sediment particles are more likely to settle. Studies from the Great Barrier Reef indicate a higher prevalence of diseased colonies in areas affected by nearby sediment plumes from reclamation and dredging activity (Pollock et al. 2016).

Solandt and Hammer (2017), in their report of the 2016 expedition, were the first to propose the ‘inner/outer reef dichotomy’, namely that shallow nature of reefs adjacent to deep water, the potential for upwellings and being close to a reef channel (the passage between the inner and outer reef with depths of at least 20 m) allows for considerable water exchange in volume, which affects temperature. This is markedly different from inner reefs, particularly those lying deep within atolls, which are more likely to be affected by increased water temperature, and which have more stagnant water between tides. This was corroborated by Cowburn et al. (2019) in a study using Current/Temperature/Depth loggers at Rasdhoo Madivaru.

Pancrazi et al. (2025), co-authored by the report authors, and heavily relying on Reef Check data collected by Biosphere Expeditions, illustrate typical trajectories of ‘recovery’ of coral reefs, first recorded in the expedition reports: There is poor recovery of diversity of lifeforms and species from most inner reefs, with a dominance of smaller (<30 cm diameter) and slow-growing bleaching-tolerant lifeforms persisting in most of the survey locations. This is alarming, because - whilst our observations are from a few (10s) of sites visited every other year - incidental reports and spot-dives from other locations show similar trends of decline in the diversity of species, lifeforms and the very seascape on which the islands are built.

Figure 2.4b. Anchorage of MV Theia in the backreef area (see red mark) of Guriadhoo (above) that has seen extensive sand island reclamation since 2019, as can be seen from the Google Earth image (below). Surveys in 2019 (Solandt and Hammer 2020) just preceded the reclamation works starting in early 2020. Sites were re-visited in 2022 to record any effect from the reclamation on Guraidhoo backreef and forereef sites (Solandt and Hammer 2023), with results showing lower coral cover in 2022 than in 2019 surveys in locations very close to reclaimed land (Guraidhoo shallow backreef).

Pancrazi et al. (2025) followed pre- and post-bleaching trajectories of coral health from four sites in Ari atoll and used three sites visited by expeditions since 2011 (and before that by the lead author in 2005). The study showed that coral reefs are becoming less complex over time, with infestations of carpet anenomes (corallimorphs, particularly *Discosoma*) that opportunistically colonise over corals in some shallow habitats. *Acropora* are increasingly absent/rare or small in most reefs as they get killed outright from bleaching events, whilst more resilient *Porites* lifeforms persist via resistance to bleaching, and being on reefs influenced by cooler oceanic currents on outer slopes and reef crests.

An archipelago in (a largely ignored) crisis

Reef Check surveys do not distinguish between hard coral species, genus or lifeform data, as this kind of fine analysis cannot be expected from citizen scientists over short expeditions. Nevertheless, the professional scientists on the expedition have observed significant changes in lifeforms since the lead author started surveys in 2005. *Acropora* corals are not coping well with repeated bleaching events. It is now rare to see table *Acopora* lifeforms within central atolls that are greater than 30 cm in diameter. *Pocillopora* branching colonies are at least as numerous as *Acropora* colonies on exposed forereefs. Backreefs from these survey sites are almost entirely lacking in *Acropora*, with diverse lifeforms apparent such as more bleaching-tolerant forms *Porites rus* and *P. cylindrica* (the latter in more sediment dominated sites) starting to fill the very shallow-water in niches that staghorn and delicate branching *Acropora* lifeforms used to dominate. Farish Faru (that this expedition could not visit due to poor weather) was a site with these coral lifeforms that were persisting, but in an isolated location.

With climate breakdown now locked in for at least the next 20+ years (Sully at al. 2019, Brown and Caldera 2017, Zickfield and Herrington 2015), the impacts have been and will be multifarious and overwhelmingly negative, threatening the very existence of the archipelago (climate models predict that most of the Maldives islands will be underwater within 50 years, e.g. Viner and Agnew 2000⁸), and the continuation of the global human civilisation as we know it today. The Maldives are on course for devastating impacts on coral assemblages, reef fish populations (Sattar et al. 2012, Richardson et al. 2018) and on the general health of the coral reef ecosystem and abundance of the marine life surrounding the islands (Montano et al. 2015, Norstrom et al. 2009, Saponari et al. 2014). None of this is new information – and this is perhaps the problem – with cognitive bias leading to inaction (Palmucci & Ferraris 2023).

The existential decline of Maldives coral reefs began in the 1990s with the first global coral mass-bleaching event in 1998, compounded by the development of commercial fisheries and the large-scale expansion of the tourism infrastructure. Successive Maldivian governments – as elsewhere in the world – have perniciously ignored, downplayed or attempted to discredit the warning signs. Worse, they have locked the Maldives into debt to foreign investors for generations⁹ ¹⁰, whilst at the same time reducing or destroying

⁸ <https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/cru/posters/2000-11-DV-tourism.pdf>

⁹ <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-maldives-election-debt-idUSKCN1LY1QR>

¹⁰ <https://www.tourism-watch.de/en/article/maldives-island-state-in-debt/>

environmental natural capital (seagrass beds, fish stocks, and coral reefs)¹¹ ¹² and aggressively growing resort and tourist numbers¹³ ¹⁴ without parallel development of environmental precaution or the “polluter pays” principle that is within UK and EU laws. Add to this a ‘green tax’¹⁵ without a process for public or civil society to tap into green tax funds, or projects or programmes to track marine environmental quality and trends for improving adaptive management and environmental governance, and a series of ‘paper parks’ (MPAs that only exist on paper). Overall the outlook is bleak (even if there are new efforts by IUCN to combat the paper park problem¹⁶).

Many Maldivians would argue that industrialisation, tourism and fisheries have helped to provide jobs for Maldivian citizens. This is undoubtedly true, the question is at what cost: As a result of over-exploitation, development, and climate breakdown, the Maldivian environment is now less able to deliver local food (fish), coastal protection, homes, and a clean environment to its people. Infrastructure, such as capital investment in waste treatment, reef habitat protection, or creation and fish population enhancement tools, are needed to ‘buffer’ resort or other commercial development. Investment in people through capacity building is also needed to better manage the marine environment and the resources it provides.

Regular monitoring of sites informing the international community of the health status of Maldives reefs has predominantly been undertaken by outside agencies (IUCN, local NGOs, international scientists, Reef Check, Biosphere Expeditions), until bleaching events occur. When bleaching does occur, there is usually budget released to undertake surveys by internal MRC staff. Biosphere Expeditions can continue to monitor reefs, but without enforcement, boats, trained officers, surveillance of vessels, and a judiciary that prosecutes those that fish in MPAs and damage the coral reefs, there will be little support for conservation from the wider population (Zubair et al. 2011). Only after investments are made in coral reef protection, fisheries restrictions, and water and waste treatment, will conservation start to deliver for people. In addition, proper financial accounting of healthy marine ecosystems¹⁷ would help to showcase the importance of nature for the country’s wellbeing¹⁸, but this is nowhere in sight.

To compound the problem, many Maldives citizens hold scepticism towards western-funded conservation work. This is likely a result of finance from western companies historically supporting unsustainable foreign investment at odds with the cultural norms (e.g. de Vos, 2020), as much as ‘parachute science’¹⁹.

¹¹ <https://theconversation.com/the-maldives-is-threatened-by-rising-seas-but-coastal-development-is-causing-even-more-pressing-environmental-issues-170144>

¹² <https://www.climatechangenews.com/2022/03/25/maldives-greenlights-destructive-dredging-to-build-housing-and-luxury-resorts/>

¹³ <https://www.tourism.gov.mv/dms/document/f5f522de183dde8f0f012884cecb1706.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://tourism.gov.mv/en/registered/facilities/filter-t1>

¹⁵ <https://www.mira.gov.mv/Pages/View/whatisgreentax>

¹⁶ <https://iucn.org/story/202506/paper-practice-turning-maldives-protected-areas-real-conservation-models>

¹⁷ <https://www.dropbox.com/s/0b64j69s76et3r8/Summary%20-%20bottom-contact%20fishing%20MPA%20report%20%281%29.pdf?dl=0>

¹⁸ <https://www.gresham.ac.uk/watch-now/series/natural-capital>

¹⁹ [Parachute science falls to earth | News | Nature Index](#)

Solutions

We believe that an entirely different approach is needed to manage the Maldives: a system whereby power is granted to atoll councils with a need to sustain local economies and growth, all within environmental limits. This will also result in well-being and security for local islands and populations, with funding available for local infrastructure moved away from private to public areas (e.g. better housing, schools, shoreline protection, MPA and fisheries enforcement).

Clearly the environmental assets that allow income for foreign markets do not ‘feed the nation’, but do provide large incomes for a few within the political and business elite. The UK and many western economies have also seen recent wealth gaps between the richest and poorest, with associated declines in the state of society²⁰. Improper, piecemeal and apologetic environmental management from government mirrors the loss of social support for communities (e.g. health care, libraries, public spaces, transport infrastructure, education, water treatment).

The Maldives is a ‘canary in the coal mine’ for global environmental degradation and the result of unbalanced power structures²¹. The concerning situation of the past can improve, but only if the current administration delivers a greater proportion of the profits (largely from tourism) into public services and proper environmental protection. The Maldives government has the power to make the ‘paradise effect’ of the Maldives help to pay for its recovery.

The recently published Hanifaru Bay research and monitoring plan (EPA and MoTE 2025) shows how both public, private and volunteers can be combined to provide useful monitoring of a protected area. This model needs to be applied with a similar finance mechanism throughout key sentinel sites and MPAs throughout the archipelago to ensure resilient protection and stakeholder support.

Conclusions

There are back-reef hard coral lifeforms that are becoming more dominant as they are more resistant to bleaching such as extensive stands of *Porites rus*. This species can assume many different morphologies, somewhat replacing the ecological role of a diverse range of historically dominant *Acropora* species. Our findings from long-term studies (Pancrazi et al. 2025) revealed that this transition to a low diversity *Acropora* state (particularly in shallow forereefs) is common throughout the central Maldives. Furthermore, on a greater scale, the older colonies on these reefs are becoming increasingly rare, with small colonies emerging from the base coral bedrock the norm at a seascape scale. Disease and *Drupella* predation are further affecting *Acropora* health (i.e. their overall resilience and resistance to temperature change). *Acropora* corals are also highly susceptible to Crown of Thorns predation compared to other species, due to their large fleshy polyps (compared to smaller *Porites* polyps), vastly increasing their preference for this predator (Millican et al. 2024).

²⁰ <https://theconversation.com/dont-listen-to-the-rich-inequality-is-bad-for-everyone-81952>

²¹ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/justice-home-affairs/opinion/unbalanced-politics-leads-to-unchecked-power/>

The loss of older, larger colonies, and the once great physical complexity offered by a healthy mix of old *Acropora* corals represents a significant reduction in the physical 3-D habitat into which reef fish can settle and then take shelter, putting additional pressure on an already strained ecosystem.

The conclusions and recommendations below are the same as in previous reports, as little has changed and there is still little concerted top-down effort to deal with on-the-ground solutions to building environmental resilience in the Maldives.

After 15 years of annual Reef Check surveys, we posit that there are broadly two different types of reef and call this the ‘inner/outer reef dichotomy’:

1. **Exposed outer (oceanic) reefs** are associated with greater currents, wave action, and are adjacent to very deep water. These areas are generally more resilient to bleaching because of the dominance of greater bleaching-resistant coral lifeforms and the cooler, deeper adjacent seawater (Cowburn et al. 2019).
2. **Inner reefs** are dominated by temperature-intolerant species such as branching *Acropora* and *Pocillopora*, which are subsequently more vulnerable to disease, pollution and sedimentation, *Drupella* and Crown of Thorns predation, and sponge/algal recruitment and growth. In the central atolls of the Maldives, inner reefs are dominated by coral rock and turf algae. They may still be able to recruit corals and grow back to being coral dominated (e.g. Kudafalhu in central Ari), compared to those that have recruited ‘pest’ species such as *Discosoma* corallimorphs that appear to have few predators. It would seem from the literature that there may be a ‘resort’ affect, with lower recovery trajectories after bleaching being observed at inhabited reefs – but this is highly variable (e.g. Montefalcone et al. 2020).

We observe the following status of the reefs:

- A. In general, outer reefs that are exposed to colder oceanic waters appear to be more resilient than inner reefs that suffer more heat, pollution, fishing and nutrient stress.
- B. Some inner reefs are exhibiting a phase shift from a coral-dominated state to an algal, sponge and *Discosoma* (non-coral) state (e.g. Dega Thila).
- C. Some inner (S Male’ atoll) reefs have adapted to climate-induced bleaching with more bleaching- and sediment-tolerant coral species, e.g. *Porites cylindrica* and *P. rus* persisting or outcompeting *Acropora* recruits, sponge, algae, and other competitors (e.g. southern Baros, Guraidhoo backreef and Beybe’s).
- D. Certain reefs show some resistance to bleaching impacts, supporting species that were hitherto described as having low thermal tolerance (e.g. Farish faru in Vaavu) with large thickets of *Acropora* corals in deeper (>15m) water. The greater shelter and deeper nature of the colonies may have released these colonies from shallow water extreme SSTs during bleaching (waters under 5m). Note that this is the rarest form of reef we observed in our surveys since the 2016 bleaching event.

Our recommendations on issues related to coral reef vulnerability have been highlighted in previous reports available from the Biosphere Expeditions page on [ResearchGate](#). Our observations and training will hopefully increase awareness, but this is only within the survey teams aboard our vessels. Research has shown that recovery projections from coral bleaching events become more protracted over time, whilst more frequent bleaching events occur. Therefore, the Maldives will likely need decades to recruit and grow corals to resemble the reefs before the 1998 bleaching event. However, with the 2024 bleaching event occurring just four years after the last event, the ability to be resilient to such events is being tested more than ever before. As such, it is likely that the coral reefs will never regenerate to the levels seen in 1997 and before, and indeed, the species guilds – of hard corals at the very least – will be very different, particularly for inner atoll reefs.

Our recommendations are:

1. Invite either the EPA, or each atoll council, environmental officers to be present (with an office, officials, and boats) on each island atoll to control unsustainable fishing, dredging, and construction. Re-visiting the de-centralisation act would help facilitate local protection.
2. Fund and train sufficient EPA officers and atoll council law courts and enforcement officers to arrest and fine people who break environmental rules/laws in MPAs and at island house reefs. A Protected Areas Act with a duty to monitor and enforce could enable progress in this area.
3. Fund the EPA to investigate & prosecute (fine) tourism or other developments where environmental damage is being caused (such as sediment outflows on live healthy reefs) above levels stated in Environment Impact Assessments. Enable EPA to do its job properly by divesting funds from developers to enforcers such that they have the staff and materials to effectively enforce their duties.
4. EPA officials must have knowledge of pristine (or semi-pristine) environmental baseline conditions to assess the relative scale of impact. They need funding to visit healthy undisturbed reefs in remote parts of the archipelago to support them.
5. Ensure that fisheries department officials work collaboratively with the EPA in assessing fisheries' activities at resorts, grouper cages²², processing facilities, and at airports.
6. Ensure that every resort has to enact reef enhancement programmes that are not solely based on the construction of reef walls, but enable the development and growth of reef pyramids and fore-reef coral structures to allow sustainable growth under the water of a living wave barrier. Ensure advice from the MRC scientists and engineers is used to guide these efforts.

²² Grouper cages exist in at least five atolls where fish are corralled before being shipped to Asian 'live fish' markets.

7. Introduce size limits on grouper fisheries as previously recommended to government (Wood et al., 2011, Evans et al. 2018), which include:
 - a. regulated fishing.
 - b. mandatory logbooks and data collection.
 - c. long-term monitoring of catch, abundance, and spawning aggregation sites.
 - d. national level awareness-raising programme.
 - e. a mobile-phone technology Vessel Monitoring Scheme (VMS) for Maldives-registered fishing vessels such that enforcement can be done by using satellite technology²³.
8. Ensure that the fisheries department have enforcement officers based at fish cages to ensure that grouper size limits are met.
9. Ensure that EPA and fisheries department officers are stationed at or near to protected grouper spawning aggregation sites.
10. Ensure that the EPA is provided enough budget (via, for example, a tourism tax) to enable it to be present (with an officer) on tourist islands and enforce law and, if necessary, prosecute.
11. Ensure that the MRC is enabled, through an environment tax, to undertake rapid reef health assessment monitoring at all Maldivian resorts as a matter of law, and that the reports from the standard monitoring assessment are annually reported to government and made public.
12. Ensure all enforcement, fines, and prosecutions under the powers of the EPA and fisheries department are vetted by an independent body of accountants, lawyers, and governance experts, including officials, managers, and scientists from the EPA, MRC, and the Fisheries Department of the Maldives.

²³ Global Fishing Watch is used by Governments to assess illegal fishing activities in real time:
<https://globalfishingwatch.org/>

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